

D4.11 Technical Documentation of R5, R6 and R7: **Apps**

FDEUSTO

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Executive Summary

The current deliverable focuses on the technical details behind the design of the apps (R5-R7).

Section 1 makes an introduction about the concepts behind the R5-R7 eco-solutions. It highlights the domain details and discusses the decisions taken around their design. Section 2 gives an overview of the main functionalities of the apps according to the scope and objectives of Waste4Think. Section 3 describes the integration and communication with the rest of the Waste4Think ecosystem, especially with the ContextBroker. Section 4 details the technologies that used for the implementation of the apps in terms of front-end, back-end, and continuous testing. Section 5 details the KPIs in terms of waste management and the impact of the eco-solution itself that are measured by the usage of these apps. Section 6 details the approach that ensures the quality of the product through a methodology of continuous delivery and testing procedures. Section 7 and Sections 8 list the main functionalities of the Food App and the Citizen App respectively, describing also the entities for the data model and giving an overview of the mock-ups to better describe how each of them can be used.

Glossary

CIF/VAT numbers	National identification number that identify business to state revenue services.
Citizen empowerment	The process of making the citizens part of the decision-making process.
ContextBroker	A software middleware that maintains an image of the current status of all the devices monitored by a system.
DIY kit	A kit designed to be self-explanatory and have all the necessary elements to make some small project.
Donor	A person who receives a donation.
Donee	A person who donates.
Ecological footprint	The measured global impact that a human process and its complementary processes have on the natural resources.
Front-end	The software that is directly accessed by the users and is responsible for the interaction with them.
Gantt diagram	A time diagram used to display task planification, usually detailed in subtasks.
GUI	Graphic User Interface. The interface (images, shapes and words) that a software shows to the user to communicate with him/her.
Hybrid app	An application for mobile devices that uses native code and features, and is also a web app.
(ICT)	Information and communications technology. A term that includes all the technologies for communication and processing of data in digital form.
KPIs	Key performance Indicator. The quantitative indicators that provide a general indication of a progress.
Large generators	Entities that generate large amount of food surpluses.
Mock-ups	A sketched design of human machine interface used during the early process of software design.
NACE codes	A classification of economic activities in the European Community for statistical purposes.
PAYT	Pay as you throw: A variable tax that is based on the citizen's use of the waste disposal system.
QR Code	A well-known bidimensional barcode standard that can contain quick readable data (numeric, alphanumeric, byte/binary, and kanji) and is easily read by smart mobiles.
RESTful interface	An application interface (API) build over a collection of callable Web services that conform a REST architecture.
SSO-Single Sign On	The process to share the user's identification process over several different applications or webs, usually to avoid repeating the login process for each one.
Food waste	Waste produced for the food discarded or expired, usually coming for surplus or stockage.
WebView	A technology used to show a web app as a native Android application. Very useful for development of multi-platform solutions.

1. Introduction

When the waste management term comes up it is easy to think about how much, when, what and where this waste is, even if this generation comes from domestic citizens, schools, or enterprises. In this context, mobile applications (Apps) play an important role as: they will help to exploit all this detailed real-time information from citizens over the different collections systems (Pilots) fostering citizen participation and involvement which is one of the main challenges of the Waste4Think project.

To this end, initially, the development of three applications was foreseen:

- The Food App (R5) for edible food waste prevention. With the support of a real-time characterization system, this app will allow citizens and enterprises to advertise the products that continue to be in good condition but are going to be thrown and to implement cost-effective processes for their collection and retrieval by social kitchens, for example. With a prevention approach the app will also give information to the generators (large generators as supermarkets or restaurants, but also citizens in general) about their daily generation patterns.
- The Local Trade app (R6) for fostering sustainable local trade and eco-tourism by:
 - Getting to know the incentives achieved by their behaviour, etc.
 - Getting information about the ways they can get incentives and the offers where they can use them (such as discount vouchers on business).
 - Getting information about the environmental (as the ecological footprint) and social impacts of the products and services that have been used in their neighbourhoods.
 - Getting information about the businesses that have implemented ecological products or services such as the use of good practices on waste prevention (use recyclable bags...).
 - Getting information about the correct way of sorting a product through the QR code of the envelope.
 - Getting to know about the cooperative actions in the municipality such as composting or other decentralized treatment solutions.
 - Sharing and recycling furniture, appliances, clothing, toys, etc
- The Citizen App (R7) to foster transparency and citizen participation by providing interfaces for the components of the system that citizen and enterprise managers will use to get and send information about the state of the collection system. The app will also:
 - Allow consulting the invoices and retrieving information about citizen behaviour as well as the overall state of the waste collection system in the municipality like the economic, environmental and social impacts.
 - Send incidents in the collection spots like overfilled bins, broken infrastructures, etc.
 - Provides tips to improve the way of sorting, reduce the waste generated or information about the clean points.
 - Allow citizens to get access to the bill information or submit issues about the collection system.

However, after consultation with experts and stakeholders, and taking into account market and usability issues, it was decided that, while the Food App would remain as a standalone app, the Citizen App and the Local Trade App would be merged into a single app, named from now on *Sustainable City App (R6-R7)*. This approach will also allow to maximize the impact among residential and non-residential profiles.

In this deliverable, a detailed overview is covered about the technical considerations of the design, development and implementation of these applications, as well as their relationship with other modules and features within the Waste4Think ecosystem. The *Food App (R5)* and the *Sustainable City App (R6-R7)* represent handy-tools that will allow citizens to manage the gathered information, whether public (from their communities) or private (from themselves), to improve the individual and collective behaviour about waste management and prevention habits, learn how to optimize the sorting rates and use of resources, share their feedback with others, help improve the collection system on the issues reports and as a final purpose taking care of the environment.

Please note this report is also linked with the following deliverables:

- *D1.1 Pilot Planning documentation* for information about the functional requirements of R5-R7 and use cases.
- *D1.2. Best Practices Database in Circular Economy, Economic Instruments and Prevention Actions* for information about the best practices database in circular economy.
- *D1.3 Sustainability Assessment Models* for information about the user requirements, the definition of the criteria to evaluate the sustainability regarding food waste prevention and local trade and the set of the KPIs defined to monitor waste management systems as well as the impact of the use of the Apps.
- From *D1.4 Preparatory Actions Report* to *D1.7 Full Test Report* for details about the progress and time schedule of the development, testing and delivery of the apps.
- *D2.1 Technical Documentation of R1: Operation and Management Module* for information about the technical details behind digital the architecture of the Waste4Think components.
- *D2.9 Technical Documentation of R4: Circular Economy Planning Module* for information about the module of Circular Economy.
- *D4.2. Implementation of R17: ICT based Innovative Social Actions* for information about the content and methodology behind the implementation of the information featured by the apps.
- *D5.1 Technical Documentation of the Invoicing Module for R2* and *D5.3 New Regulations to Implement PAYT Systems (R16)* for details about the specific of the implementation of the PAYT system in the different pilots.
- *D6.1. Exploitation and IPR report* and *D6.2. Identification of key results and functional analysis of each key result* for information about the exploitation plan for the apps after the end of the projects.

The status of the development for the R4.11 is provided in **the Monitoring Action Reports (Deliverables D1.4 to D1.7)**.

2. Functional overview

The *Food App* (R5) and *Sustainable City App* (R6-R7) are web-based applications that can be accessed from mobile devices (smartphones, iPad/tablets) with Android/iOS and from computers (desktop web browsers). In both cases these applications feature a proper viewport configuration and design focused on optimal user experience as detailed on Sections 7 and 8.

Every app will have an **About** section with:

- App logo, description and purpose
- Privacy Policy
- Legal Attributions
- Copyright

2.1 Usage

Generally, there are three approaches when developing apps for mobile phones:

- **Native App Development:** Native apps are built for specific platforms and are written in the languages the platform accepts (for example, Swift and Objective-C are common languages for iOS apps and Java or Kotlin are common for Android apps). Native apps are fast and responsive, distributed in app stores, offer intuitive user input and output, and don't require an internet connection. Overall, native apps offer a better user experience but are more expensive to develop than other options
- **Web App Development:** Web apps are hosted on web browsers and are essentially websites that look like native apps. However, instead of installing the application to the device's home screen, like a native app, users interact with the app through a WebView. This type of app is easy to build, easy to maintain and an inexpensive option; however, they require a web browser, are much slower than native apps, and can't leverage device utilities.
- **Hybrid App Development:** Hybrid apps are essentially a combination of native and web apps. A hybrid app consists of two parts: the first is the back-end code, and the second is a native shell that is downloadable and loads the code using a WebView. Hybrid apps are less expensive than native apps, don't require a browser, and can leverage device APIs. A hybrid app can be downloaded from the official app stores and installed on the user's phone, just like a native app would do.

Both the Food App and Sustainable City App will be hybrid apps. This approach provides great flexibility during the development and deployment phases because any update in the hybrid app will become immediately available to all devices since the content is coming from one centralized location. The update of the app is completely transparent to the user, so we assure that he/she is always using the latest version. Instead, for the native app, the changes would have to be performed separately for each different supported platform (Android, iOS), built again, and go over the time-consuming app certification process in order to make the update available via all of the app stores.

Therefore, the decision to implement the Waste4Think apps as hybrid apps was taken with the purpose to focus on the apps usage and functionalities instead of their maintenance in different operating systems (Android, iOS, desktop) which would require a lot of effort in terms of maintenance i.e. if there is a new version of the operating system or some of the native mobile functionalities change. Moreover, a large number of functionalities will feed directly from the information provided directly by the public Observatory described in Deliverable D2.1 Technical Documentation of R1: Operation and Management Module, therefore a hybrid app implementation facilitates their integration in a cross-domain application that is available either from PCs (web browsers as usual) and from mobile markets: Google Play Store (Android) and Apple App Store (iOS).

2.2 Scope & Objectives

The main objective of this set of mobile applications (Apps) is to facilitate collaborative tools for citizen empowerment and engagement to move towards more sustainable and inclusive cities. Due to its global accessibility by everyone from everywhere, citizen, commerce and public in general would be interested in this kind of initiatives about using collaborative tools to improve their citizen behaviours with society and environment.

For the purpose of the Waste4Think Project, these Apps are a set of collaborative and informative tools that will provide an active bi-directional communication channel contributing to the following specific objectives (SO) of Waste4Think

SO1. To **reduce the generation of waste** thanks to the implementation of cost-effective prevention campaigns and the promotion of cooperative activities to boost the reuse and more sustainable consumption models.

SO2. To **promote the long-term behavioural changes of waste generators** (citizens and industries) by fostering transparency, citizen empowerment and engagement.

SO4. To **eliminate the primary waste deposited into landfills** and to maximize waste reuse and recycling.

SO5. To **promote the creation of new government and business models** moving towards a circular economy

Waste4Think Apps will allow:

- To prevent food waste opening a channel for food donation and informing about best practices according to the kind of generator
- To access information about the waste management system in general, and about individual behaviour, in particular
- To provide tips to improve individual behaviour
- To open a channel to share and participate with best practices in circular economy at domestic and local trade levels

Target audience

The target audience of the apps will be:

- Domestic citizens (domestic)
- Enterprises/industries (domestic users)
- Educational centres/schools

Language

The apps will be available in English and on the native language of the four pilots:

- Spanish & Euskara – Zamudio (Basque Country, Spain)
- Portuguese – Cascais (Portugal)
- Italian – Seveso (Italy)
- Greek- Halandri (Greece)

Accessibility

The Waste4Think apps will be developed including some elements from the *accessibility guidelines* of the WAI initiative¹ to ensure they can be used by everyone regardless of disabilities creating high quality tools with an easy and optimal design that provide equal access to participate actively on the waste management.

Figure 1 shows the accessibility functionalities that will be included:

Perceivable information and user interface	Operable user interface and navigation	Understandable information and user interface	Robust content and reliable interpretation
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-text content with text alternatives • Multimedia with captions • Content is presented in different ways • Content easy to see/hear 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • App options are available from a keyboard • Content and texts are easy to read and use • Content can be find and accessed easily 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • App options are readable and understandable • Content appears/operates in predictable ways • Users are helped to avoid and correct mistakes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • App content is compatible with user tools

Figure 1. Accessibility functionalities of the apps.

Content, multimedia & icons

All icons, images, videos, and any content on the design and development of the Food App and Sustainable City App will be labelled for commercial use/reuse and modification; in any case, with the Creative Commons license. In that cases when some references are needed to include (links to the web, documents, etc.) i.e. as help or additional information, the author will be asked directly about it and the Waste4Think Project will not be responsible for the maintenance of this sources.

¹ <https://www.w3.org/WAI/>

2.3 User Stories

Ane is a citizen of Zamudio. She is very concerned with the environment and because of that, she is strongly focused on being as environmentally friendly as she can. For example, Ane makes her own compost in her house, sorts her waste in all the fractions, and tries to buy only in sustainable shops.

a) Sustainable City App

Ane is planning to throw a big party to celebrate the birth of her first nephew. She plans to invite all her family and friends. She expects to have at least 40 people in her garden. She must buy a lot of things for the party, including the food, the decoration and a present for her nephew. She went to her favourite grocery store where she knows that she will find sustainable products. Unfortunately, the grocery store is closed. Ane does not know of any other grocery store that provides sustainable products, but she knows that the Local Trade app provides this information. Ane opens the app and looks for a grocery store nearby that has the products she needs. She fills in the form with all the products she needs, and the app shows the list of nearby shops. She picks the first one and goes there.

Ane now needs a pergola to give shelter to the guests. Once again, she uses the app to look for a shop that has this type of product, but unfortunately, she does not find any. Ane goes to the hardware store nearby and buys a pergola. While she was shopping there, she realized that the hardware store had opened a repair shop, where they also build furniture with wood from a local and sustainable forest. This information was not in the Local Trade app, so she fills in a form and sends it so that everyone in the community is aware of the existence of this new local and sustainable service. Ane is also part of an NGO that meets every Sunday to collect plastics from the municipal parks. So, she decides to share this initiative also in the area of new practices in order to look for more volunteers that may join.

Ane's party has already finished. It was quite fun, but now she has a big amount of waste in her house that she does not know how to manage. First, Ane tries to sort all the waste she and her guests have made but holds several doubts with some of the items. There are several packages that she does not know whether they can be thrown to the blue container or to the yellow one. She remembers that the Sustainable City App has a utility to solve this type of doubts. She opens the app, looks for the specific packaging and sees that, in this case, they should be thrown to the brown container! She was very surprised, but as she is making her own compost, she put this package in her auto composting zone. She has several other doubts that the app can solve easily.

Ane is now happy. She has finally classified all the wastes but has a small problem: her nephew used a large number of nappies while he was there. The app tells Ane that this fraction should not be put in the rest fraction since it is a particular fraction. Ane does not know what to do with it. Nevertheless, the Sustainable City App has also a tool to locate the nearest point where she can dispose every fraction. She opens the app and looks for the correct deposit point in which to deposit the nappies. She finds one just two blocks away! She is happy that she will be able to clean all the mess made in the party.

But Ane is very curious about this new container for nappies. She wants to know more about it. She knows that the Sustainable City App have information about the waste management system, so she opens it and starts browsing. She finds the information she was looking for: in order to improve the sorting rate, the municipality has implemented a PAYT (Pay As You Throw) scheme which is depending on the individual generation of residual waste. So, in order not to punish those families which generate nappies the municipality has decided to collect separately the nappies. This stings her curiosity to know better her behaviour and understand the calculation of her invoice and visits the area called "My behaviour" to know more about that.

Finally, when she goes to the nappies container to throw them, she finds it is broken. Thanks to the App she sends this incident to the waste collector who comes quickly to repair it. Since Ane's other neighbours have provided evaluation about the position of the containers though the App, the manager decides to change also their location to improve accessibility.

Ane is even happier now as she has realized the positive impact that her efforts have had.

b) Food App

Ane has bought a lot of prepared food for the party from a canteen and, as usual, she has a lot of leftovers. She does not want to throw them away, so she speaks with the canteen to look for a solution. Thus, the canteen informs Ane that they usually use an App called "Food App" in order to reduce the current food waste.

The responsible of the canteen has already registered and creates "a surpluses alarm". Thanks to this alarm, it is possible to take a picture of the surpluses from the party and add some information about some basic characteristics of the surpluses such as the type of food, cooked/non-cooked, the weight and a photograph. Using this data, it is possible to publish the food so as to obtain a potential donee for these surpluses.

After an hour, the canteen receives a notification from the Food App. One potential donee (an NGO which works with a charity kitchen) was interested in the collection of the surpluses. Thanks to the app, the donor could also read the basic information of this donee. The name of the donee is Mikel, he has already collected food from other alerts twenty-three times, and his comments are excellent.

For that, the canteen decides to accept the transaction using the app and they met at 17:00 pm in the canteen. Finally, the canteen can consult some information about all its donations such as the historical data and the avoided environmental impact due to the food donation as well as tips in order to improve the consumption habits of the restaurant. Moreover, thanks to the use of that app, Ane has avoided wasting her surpluses and she also had the opportunity to help her neighbourhood.

3. Back-End: Integration within the W4T architecture

As previously specified on Deliverable *D2.1. Technical Documentation of R1: Operation and Management Module*, the Back-End of the Waste4Think project is defined by three different systems under a wide infrastructure based on FIWARE-LAB technologies: a GitLab development environment, a Back-End management system with the FIWARE technologies and the Front-End systems to monitoring tools.

This architecture allows the development and integration of the *Food App* (R5) and *Sustainable City App* (R6-R7) as follows:

- using security components for the SSO-Single Sign On across the authentication and authorization systems (login to the private citizen zone for the proper info management)
- collecting all the public/private data (information in real-time and historical) to its visualization/usage (sorting waste searching, waste collection scheduling, PAYT information, dashboard, stats, images, available incentives and best practices, etc.)
- getting context information from the Pilots via public/private APIs subscriptions and RESTful interfaces (FIWARE GE -generic enablers)
- subscribing to the event notifications/alerts (ORION - ContextBroker GE)

Figure 2. Relation of R5-R7 within the overall architecture of Waste4Think.

Figure 2 shows the relationship of the Food App (R5) and Sustainable City App (R6-R7) with the rest of the components of the Waste4Think architecture.

The Sustainable City App (R6-R7) will communicate with the ContextBroker (R1) and the Persistence module (R1) to retrieve the information already available about the configuration of the waste management system of the pilot from which the user. This information will vary depending on the pilot from which the user is accessing the app. The data available in the ContextBroker that will be used by the Sustainable City App is as follows:

- The type of the different fractions that are collected, the wastes that can be gathered by each fraction, the location of the deposit points, etc.
- Data about new campaigns or social actions that are being carried out in the pilot or have already been carried out.
- Data about the nearest deposit points belonging to a certain fraction.
- Data about the state of the waste management system, such as the recycling rate over time, the amount of waste collected, etc.
- Data about the best practices regarding commerce not only by querying but also by subscribing to the notifications.
- The invoice for the user logged into the app not only by querying but also by notification.

The Food App (R5) will communicate with the ContextBroker and the Persistence to retrieve information about food donations nearby. The user could also subscribe to the notifications is a particular donee in the area and publish Food transactions whenever an exchange is made. More details about the data model of the Sustainable City App and the Food App can be found in Section 7.2 and Section 7.3, respectively. The list of functional requirements that are common to both apps is detailed in Table 1.

Table 1. Functional requirements common to the Food App and the Sustainable City App

R5-6-7_FR1	Common functional requirements of the apps
R5-6-7_FR1.1	There are four profiles of users: generator, receptor, public administration, root
R5-6-7_FR1.1.1	The system should be able to use the municipal authentication system
R5-6-7_FR1.1.2	The system should be able to use OpenID authentication system
R5-6-7_FR1.2	Provide aggregated information to R1_FR4.1
R5-6-7_FR1.2.1	Provide aggregated information about the prevention campaigns to the monitoring system (R1_FR4.1)
R5-6-7_FR1.2.2	Provide aggregated information about the use of the app to the monitoring system (R1_FR4.1)

The list of functional requirements specific to the Food App is detailed in Table 2.

Table 2. Functional requirements specific to the Food App.

R5_FR1	Coordinate the collection of food for social kitchens to reduce the edible food waste
R5_FR1.2	To characterize the edible food waste (for domestic generators)
R5_FR1.2.1	Identify the generator
R5_FR1.2.2	Identify the place where the surplus is generated

R5_FR1.2.3	Record the time of publication of the surplus alert
R5_FR1.2.4	Assess the quality of the food waste
R5_FR1.2.4.1	Identify the type of food (cereals, roots and tubers, oil crops and pulses, fruits and vegetables, meat, fish or dairy)
R5_FR1.2.4.2	Identify if it was cooked/uncooked
R5_FR1.2.4.3	Identify the type of preservation that the food has had. The process comprising the most important steps from purchasing to handling leftovers (cold chain, food maintenance or cooking time, if applicable).
R5_FR1.2.4.4	Identify the reason for its discarding (overproduction, spoilage, trim waste, sell-by date expired, best before date expired, aesthetic reasons, other)
R5_FR1.2.4.5	Identify other relevant information (organic product)
R5_FR1.3	Provide suggestion of all the actions that can be done with the food waste
R5_FR1.3.1	Send the surplus alert to potential receptors
R5_FR1.3.2	Provide information on the nearest collection point (composting or valorization)
R5_FR1.3.3	Suggest recipes to reuse the food waste
R5_FR1.4	To record the traceability of all the transactions
R5_FR1.5	Analyze the food waste production to give personalized tips for improving the purchase and consumption of food

The list of functional requirements specific to the Sustainable City App is detailed in

Table 3.

Table 3. Functional requirements specific to the Food App.

R6_FR1	To foster local trade, recycling and mutual learning
R6_FR1.1	Provide information about the way to get vouchers (bulletin board to publish the incentives)
R6_FR1.2	Provide information about where to redeem the vouchers (bulletin board)
R6_FR1.3	Provide information about the environmental impact of product and services (form to share sustainable product/services)
R6_FR1.4	Get and send information about the businesses that have implemented good practices
R6_FR1.5	Provide information about local cooperative actions to prevent the generation of waste
R6_FR1.5.1	Get the localization of the community composting sites (in the observatory)
R6_FR1.5.2	Get the localization of the collection of used nappies (Sort My Waste & Observatory)
R6_FR1.5.3	Allow to report new collaborative prevention actions and good practices that are being carried on (C2C best practices form)
R6_FR1.5.4	Provide aggregated information about the participation in cooperative actions to R1_FR4.1
R6_FR1.5.5	Provide integration with others providers of recycling products like Wallapop, Chiclfy, Vibbo, Milanuncios, etc.
R7_FR1	To foster transparency and citizen participation
R7_FR1.1	Show information about the waste management system
R7_FR1.1.1	Show the public information about the state of the waste management system (R1_FR4.1)
R7_FR1.1.2	Localization of the nearest collection point
R7_FR1.1.3	Localization of the clean points

R7_FR1.2	Allow to report incidences from mobile devices (R1_FR3)
R7_FR1.3	Provide information to reduce the footprint
R7_FR1.3.1	Provide information to reduce the amount of waste generated
R7_FR1.3.2	Provide information about the correct way of sorting waste
R7_FR1.4	Provide information about the PAYT system implemented
R7_FR1.5	Provide access to the invoices
R7_FR1.5.1	Review the vouchers received and redeemed so far
R7_FR1.5.2	Provide a gamification experiences to improve the awareness of the citizens

4. Technologies

The following section describes the technologies that are used to the design and develop the *Food App* (R5) and *Sustainable City App* (R6-R7) to achieve their functionalities.

4.1 Front-End

To implement the GUI- Graphic User Interface of the applications, and packaging up the functionalities (Back-End) to the visual side where users interact with, we use:

- **HTML/HTML5:** Hyper Text Mark-up Language, is the standard language for web development. We are developing with the newest version HTML5 to use a larger set of elements and technologies according to the app's requirements and modern point of view.
- **CSS/CSS3:** Cascade Style Sheet, is a style language to work on the user interface (GUI) of web applications. We are using its newest version CSS3 which includes new styles to improve borders, shadows, effects and multicolumn layout.
- **Django:** It's a free and open source web framework based on Python to build clean apps under the MVT (Model-View-Template) pattern previously described on the D2.1 document. We are developing with the last version Django 2.1.2
- **Materialize:** It's an open source framework for web responsive design and development based on Google Materialize Design. We are developing with the v1.
- **Ionic:** it's a free and an open source web framework to build mobile apps using HTML, CSS and JavaScript. We are using the Ionic 3.
- **jQuery:** It's an open source JavaScript library that simplifies the client-side scripting of HTML and events handling. We are using jQuery 3.3.1.
- **Charts.js:** It's an open source library to work with JavaScript charts and interactive graphs in a simple way on the responsive development.
- **Leaflet:** It's an easy open source JavaScript library to manage responsive (mobile-friendly and web browsers) interactive OpenStreet maps, easily customizable with CSS3 and GeoJSON.

4.2 BackEnd

To use the logical, core and technology that supports those components from the Waste4Think project architecture that together enable users to interact with the applications, we use:

- **Python:** It's a high-level programming language which allows to work and integrates systems quickly and efficiently. We are using Python 3 with the Django framework.
- **Angular:** it's a platform that makes easy the web development to desktop and mobile devices. We are using Angular 2.6
- **C# .Net:** It's an oriented object programming language under .Net framework to build robust applications. We use the C# .Net 4.7.1
- **Google Cloud Messaging (GCM):** it's a Google service to manage push notifications on Android devices.
- **ORION-FIWARE Datasources / Context:** the datasources module we access through a REST API in JSON format to retrieve all information needed to display on the different app options.
- **GitLab:** is a repository web based on the source management of the app modules we are developing.

4.3 Testing

After the first release of the applications, we use some tools to check if everything goes as expected, from the user perspective and about the functional requirements expectations. To achieve this, we use:

- **Selenium:** it's a software testing type to execute "regression tests". These test cases are done to check if the previous functionalities work fine after new changes included on the apps.
- **Appium:** it's an open source automation framework for use with hybrid and mobile web apps.
- **RedMine / JIRA:** it's an open source tool for issues tracking and management after development. In that way it's easy to follow the progress and solutions of the bugs found on the apps during the testing phase and real usage.
- **WAVE:** it's an open source tool to check through an URL the accessibility data included on the app. It analyses if the web app includes accessibility elements.

Table 4 summarizes the technologies used for the front end, the back end, and the testing for both the Food App and the Sustainable City App.

Table 4. Front end, back end and testing technologies for the Food App and the Sustainable City App.

		Food App	Sustainable City App
Front End	HTML/HTML5	x	x
	CSS/CSS3	x	x
	Django framework 2.1.2		x
	Materialize CSS framework 1		x
	Ionic	x	
	jQuery		x
	Charts.js library		x
	Leaflet maps library		x
		Food App	Sustainable City App
Back End	Python 3		x
	Angular 2.6	x	
	C# .Net 4.7.1	x	
	Google Cloud Messaging (GCM)		
	ORION -FIWARE Datasources / Context	x	x
	GitLab		
		Food App	Sustainable City App
Testing	Selenium	x	x
	Appium	x	x
	RedMine / JIRA issues tracker	x	x
	WAVE	x	x

5. Metrics and collected KPIs

The impact of the Apps will be monitored in terms of waste management and in the impact of the eco solution themselves. More details about eco-solutions KPIs can be found in Deliverable D1.3. Sustainability assessment model.

Waste4Think considers all the waste that is being collected by the 4 pilot sites: domestic waste and waste from commercial and industrial origin that has similar characteristics to those of urban waste, including food waste. Therefore, the KPIs that are being measured by the FoodApp have a direct impact on the food waste generation in the municipality. More detailed information can be found in Section 3.3.4. Characterization Matrix and Baseline Calculation procedure of deliverable D1.3

In particular, the KPIs that will be monitored thanks to the Apps will be the following ones:

a) Waste Management KPIs

Food App:

- Food waste avoided thanks to the donation of food surpluses (Kg)
- Food waste avoided per donors thanks to the donation of food surpluses (Kg/Nd)
 - Environmental impact of the food waste avoided (LCA)
- Carbon footprint of the food waste avoided (Kg CO₂ eq.)
- Water footprint of the food waste avoided (m³.)
- Nutrition data of the food waste avoided (kcal.)
- Number of exchanges with NGO collecting food waste (Ne).
- Number of donors using the Food App (Nd)
- Number of donees using the Food App (Nde)

Sustainable City App:

- Number of people saying that have modified their habits
- Level of satisfaction about the waste management systems
- Number of reported incidents
- Number of Zero Waste ecosystems

b) Impact of the eco-solutions

Table 5. Impact of the eco-solutions

		Sustainable City App	Food App
KPI-T.1	Amount of information retrieved or stored	Number of entries in the databases that could be consulted: ORION / FIWARE Best Practices -DB	Number of food transaction registered (including food offered and transferred)
KPI-T.2	Reliability of the solution	Downtime of the server provided the information (in %)	Downtime of the server provided the information (in %)
KPI-T.3	Time response of the solution	1/10000 times the time (in s) spend answering a benchmark test-suite of queries composed of: 10000 non-bota-zer queries, 10000 best practice queries and 10000 my generation queries	1/10000 times the time (in s) to register 10000 transactions
KPI-T.4	Quality of the results produced by the eco-solution	Rating by the users.	Kilograms of food donated.
KPI-S.1	Number of users	Number of downloads of the app	Number of downloads of the app
KPI-S.2	Amount of use	Number of queries answered	Number of queries answered
KPI-S.3	Satisfaction with the solution	Mean rate of the app in google play and iOS marketplace (likert)	Mean rate of the app in google play and iOS marketplace (likert)
KPI-C.2	ROI (Return on Investment) at year 2 & 5		
KPI-C.3	Payback year		
KPI-C.4	CAPEX		
KPI-C.5	OPEX		
KPI-C.6	Incomes forecast at year 2 & 5		
KPI-C.7	Break-even point		
KPI-E.1	Energy and raw materials consumption on use phase	Energy consumption (in kWh) of a development platform answering the benchmark test-suite developed for KPI-T.3	1/10000 times the energy consumption (in kWh) of a development platform registering 10000 transactions

6. Delivery and Testing

The Food App and Sustainable City App are developed under an Agile methodology (already specified on the Deliverable 2.1 Technical Documentation of R1: Operation and Management Module) which allows all the project levels involved to check, analyse and perform a proper evaluation of the current status and details whenever needed about the

1. **design:** definition of the layout, structures, components, workflows and functional - technical details of the application.
2. **development:** tasks/functionalities of the app translated to language programming.
3. **testing:** design, development and execution of test scenarios (natural happy-roads and wrong values intentionally tested) needed to check the expected results and issues (bugs) found during execution of tests. These testing tasks are performed during every sprint (app version release -phase) and are detailed in Table 6.

Table 6. Test driven development for the Sustainable City App and the Food App.

Testing type	designer developer	QA team	new tester	user candidate	testing tool	all
Functional test to ensure the app works as described with the project objectives and functional requirements <i>input:</i> -test scenarios -expected behaviour	X	X		X	X	
Usability test to ensure the app is user friendly and intuitive.	X	X	X	X		
Disabilities test to verify if the app can be used by everyone regardless of disabilities <i>input:</i> -test scenarios -expected behaviour	X	X		X	X	
Testing type	designer developer	QA team	new tester	user candidate	testing tool	all
Performance test measure how app works i.e. showing the dashboard info <i>input:</i> -test scenarios -expected performance (response time)	X	X			X	

<p>Regression test to check if the previous tasks are still working as expected after a new app version release</p>	X	X		X	X	
<p><i>input:</i> -test scenarios -expected behaviour</p>						
<p>Device test to ensure the app works properly on a wide set of mobile devices (screens sizes) and operating systems (android, iOS, Windows, Linux)</p>	X	X	X	X	X	X
<p><i>input:</i> -test scenarios -expected behaviour</p>						
<p>Focus group test a group of new testers (1st time using the app) run test scenarios and QA collect the feedback about how they use the app, what kind of issues they find and their frustrations on its usage</p>			X	X		
<p><i>input:</i> -test scenarios -expected results</p>						
<p>Beta version test to see how the app performance is on different devices, locations, operating systems, and network conditions</p>	X	X	X	X	X	X

All testing scenarios will be well documented in terms of design and execution by designers, developers and QA/Quality Assurance Team, including the results obtained after each one. A good approach can be, web-forms to collect involved data and exploit from the first to the last testing scenarios versions.

- bug fixing:** solution to the issues found during the testing phase, including new development and/or improving the existing one.

Both applications, Food App and Sustainable City App, include these phases with time duration details (specified on the Apps **Gantt diagram** in Deliverable D1.4 Preparatory Actions Report) according to the task priorities, their functionalities meaning (app-option) and project strategy considerations. This Gantt is periodically revised according to the status of the project in the monitoring reports from D1.5 to D1.7. Finally, information about how the apps will be maintained after the end of the project is available on Deliverable 6.2. Identification of key results and functional analysis of each key result.

7. Food App

The Food App, available for iOS and Android devices, is an application where food waste generators can donate their surpluses (edible food) to people or institutions who pick it up and consume it. On the other hand, generators will receive useful information about their production habits which will allow them to identify and put into practice suitable prevention initiatives according to their generation profiles.

The main functionality of the app is to bring together donors and donees in order to facilitate the donation of food surpluses, and to create awareness about the impact of food donation. The food donation model which includes the information to be retrieved about donees and food surplus as well as the KPIs to be calculated by the App are explained in Deliverable *Technical Documentation of R1: Operation and Management Module.1* and Deliverable *D1.3 Sustainability Assessment Model*.

Users within the app can play two different roles:

- donors, that publish surpluses and
- donees, that browse and request surpluses

7.1 Main functionalities

In technical terms, the Food App can be used by anyone, whether regular citizens, stores, supermarkets, NGOs, etc. The functionalities are the same in all the cases and one could use the Food App at full regardless of the background. However, it is important, prior to its use, to review whether the conditions for food donation in the area of implementation meet the needed legal regulations concerning food safety. In particular, the aim of the implementation of the Food App within the Waste4Think project intends to look after the food safety within the participants of the pilot, therefore its implementation has been carefully looked after. The main functionalities of the Food App are detailed below:

a) User account management

In order to use the app, the citizen must log in with his/her credentials. If he/she does not have an account within the Food App, he/she can create one by providing the necessary details. All this information can be later edited from the User Profile view. In this view the user can also manage the language and location settings. Typical password management screens are also included (both for recover and for change it).

Concerning the information required from the user, the Food App will ask for the following data: name, CIF if any, telephone number and address (street, town, province, postal code, and country). For statistical purposes, and in case the app is being used by other entities aside regular citizens, the Food App will ask for the economical activities to which the user is subject (Agriculture; Livestock; Hunt, fishing, aquaculture; Food manufacture; Wholesale trade; Retail; Transport; Housing (hotels, shelters, etc.); Restaurant; Restaurant catering; Education; Social and health services; Entertainment; Household).

Figure 3. Example of the “Add Surplus” option used by the donor.

While the donor is entering the characteristics of the food surplus, the Food App will give warning messages about recommendations about the optimal conditions for food donation according to Regulation (EC) No 853/2004², such as the hygiene of foodstuffs as well as considerations published by other local, and regional donation protocols. Some good examples are those published by Agencia Catalana de Seguridad Alimentaria³ or the proposal from Caritas Italiana and Fondazione Banco Alimentare⁴. These messages should make clear that the following SHOULD NOT be donated:

- Raw fish and shellfish no properly packed.
- Raw meat and derivatives no properly packed.
- Sweet and/or savoury baked products filled with unpasteurised egg-based custards or sauces.
- Cooked meals with no sauce (grilled steak, dry rice, etc.) because the difficulty of maintaining a constant temperature of 65°C.

² <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/ES/TXT/?uri=LEGISSUM%3Af84001>

³

http://www20.gencat.cat/docs/arc/Home/Ambits%20dactuacio/Prevencio/Malbaratament%20alimentari/Publicacions%20especificques/acsa_malbaratament.pdf

⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/food/sites/food/files/safety/docs/fw_library_guide-good-practice-english_2016.pdf

The donor will be also helped with messages to ensure the correct hygiene practice assuring food safety. These messages will distinguish:

- Non-cooked food: vegetables, fruits, etc.
- Cooked meals: cold and hot meals

The former will be advised to pack and label correctly the food including the recollection date. The later will include recommendations to follow correctly the temperature chain:

- Cold meals should be correctly packed maintaining a temperature below 4°C.
- Hot meals should be donated over 65°C ensuring this temperature until the consumption moment.

Notice that the donor is responsible for ensuring the adequate conditions until the delivery of the meal or food. Please see Regulation (EC) No 853/2004⁵ on the hygiene of foodstuffs for further information as well as labelling conditions. Donees, on their side, will be informed about the requirement to consume the cooked food in 24 hours. This timing would increase if the surplus is cooled using a blast chiller (5 days) or it is stored in specifically certified refrigerators (3 months).

Figure 4. Form for the publication of a food surplus.

⁵ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/ES/TXT/?uri=LEGISSUM%3Af84001>

Figure 5. Examples of list and detail of surpluses available in the donee profiles.

b) Food transaction

Once the surplus information has been entered by the donor, the surplus will be published in the Food App for the potential donees.

In fact, the main view of the app at the beginning, for the donee point of view, is a list of available surpluses. Basically, it is **a list of resources** (picture, title and some other relevant details) with “call to action” buttons. This listing can be enriched with filters, geo-position and so on. Only minimum information will be displayed. This screen is for the user to make a choice between available surpluses. Later, during the transaction, the user will get detailed information to confirm the interest.

From the donee point of view, the transaction consists of several steps. When the user is interested in a surplus:

- first, the user will **get detailed info of the surplus**
- **donor information** will be also available (contact info, users’ feedback, etc.)
- lastly, **some disclaimers and extra info** will be presented, just before the user confirms his/her interest.

The screens at the donor side are shown in Figure 5. In this step, the donor can assign the surplus to the most suitable donee. For example, the donor could assign this surplus in terms of the proximity with him/her

When a surplus is assigned to the requester, the transaction is ready to be performed physically. Being the donor the one starting the transaction operation, he/she is responsible for setting up the circumstances of the exchange (contact way, time, etc.) A random **secret password** will be shared between donor and donee (Figure 7) for security purposes.

Figure 6. Example of a request of surpluses sent to the donor.

Once the surplus is exchanged, the donor must change the **status of the transaction to “closed”**.

Both recipients and donors have then the opportunity to introduce **feedback**. This feedback can be a public or private and the format as well could be free style comments or closed answers. Public comments will be available in the user’s profiles. Private comments will be only for developing purposes to improve the user experience. Closed answers (surveys) could be automatically computed to feed the algorithms that matches donors and donees.

Furthermore, the donee will be advised to take special considerations in the case of being allergic or suffer from alimentary intolerances.

Figure 7. Example of a confirmation of the surplus request sent to the donor.

c) Best Practices

The Food App will provide give feedback about the generation patterns and their environmental impact of the donors, making them aware of the impact of their donation. According to the NACE code of the donor, some recommendations will be provided in line with Best Practices recognised by the EC (*Deliverable 1.2 Best Practices Database in Circular Economy, Economic Instruments and Prevention Actions*).

d) Statistics

The Food App will provide feedback about the impact of the food donation in terms of total kilograms of food donated, nutritional value (kcal), carbon footprint (kg CO₂ eq) and water scarcity (m³-eq) avoided.

7.2 Data model

The Food App builds upon the Waste4Think data model defined in Deliverable 2.1 Technical Documentation of R1: Operation and Management Module. Specifically, the Sustainable City App (R6-R7) will make use of the following entities:

- **User account** management (for both donor and donee profiles): FoodAppUser, KeyPerformanceIndicator
- **Publishing of surpluses:** FoodAppUser, FoodAppTransaction
- **Food transaction:** FoodAppTransaction
- **Best practices:** BestPractice

7.3 Terms of Use

A special clause for the user to accept (explicitly) the Terms and Conditions of use for the app will be included, following the current regulations on this matter. It will be based on the example provided in Annex A, which is based on the conditions of the Waste App from the Urban Waste project GA No. 690452.

Due to its nature (manage food exchanges), the Food App will include a special clause to inform the users the App is not responsible for the veracity of the information shown (ingredients of the meals –allergens-, expiration date, etc.)

These issues are under review of Waste4Think Ethical Committee.

8. Sustainable City App

The purpose of the *Sustainable City App* (R6-R7) is to facilitate and foster waste sorting management on everyday life as well as to promote more sustainable production and consumption models among citizens (residential and non-residential) on the four pilots of the Waste4Think project. The app fully complies with the KAYT (Know-As-You-Throw) approach by focusing on giving detailed continuous individual feedback about the waste management behaviour of the citizens, who feel monitored and consequently, improve their habits, by fostering participation in specific sensitization campaigns, highlighting the benefits of green initiatives in the local commerce, and also by providing information about why and where must waste be sorted correctly.

8.1 Main functionalities

The functionalities of the Sustainable City App fall within two categories according to the intended visibility and availability of the information (

Figure 8).

- **Public profile:** The functionalities that fall within this category are available for all the citizens without needing to perform any previous authentication. They are available as soon as the app is installed on the mobile phone (Dashboard, Sort My Waste, Bulletin Board, Best Practices, Lean More! and Profile Management).
- **Private profile.** The functionalities that fall within this category need the citizen to provide some credentials in order to visualize the information required. These credentials identify the citizen as unique within the waste management system and therefore provide sensible and personal information that require authentication (My Waste-O-Meter, Change Password (Profile Management)).

Figure 8. Functionalities of the Sustainable City App.

a) Dashboard

The Dashboard is the landing view of the Sustainable City App. It features an overview of the status of the waste management system in the municipality, including relevant KPIs associated

to the sorting rate per fraction, the treatment/final destination given to the waste, important notices, recommendations, the evolution of waste generation overtime, etc. It also provides a link to visualize the Public Observatory. More details about the Dashboard are available on Section 8.3.1.

b) My Waste-O-Meter

The Waste-O-meter is a **private** view. Since it contains sensitive information about the behaviour of the citizens regarding the waste management system and as such, the citizens must log in prior to accessing the content. This information covers everything related to the number of openings performed by the citizen on different containers (in the case of Zamudio and Cascais), or the number of bags used for residual waste (in the case of Seveso) and its monetary/points equivalence according to the PAYT scheme available in the municipality. This section also provides an overview of the historical data, so the citizens can follow their evolution over time. More details about the Waste-O-Meter can be found in Section 8.3.2. Also, information about PAYT in the Waste4Think pilot sites can be found in *Deliverables D5.1 Technical Documentation of the Invoicing Module for R2* and *D5.3 New Regulations to Implement PAYT Systems (R16)*.

c) Sort My Waste

The Sort My Waste view provides a search engine to help the citizen identify the container to which a specific waste must be thrown. The citizen writes down the name of the item (fingernail, apple, milk packaging, etc.) on the search box, and the results will show the nearest containers on which the item can be deposited. The citizen will also be able to filter the search to know the location of the containers of a specific fraction or of those containers opening on specific hours. More details about Sort My Waste can be found in Section 8.3.3.

d) Bulletin Board

The Bulletin Board view serves as a common point where all the relevant waste management awareness events, campaigns or ongoing cooperative actions are featured. Its purpose is to foster participation by keeping the citizen well informed about what is taking place in the municipality. More information about the Bulletin Board can be found in Section 8.3.4.

e) Best Practices

The Best Practices view provides a list of actions that has been shown by research or experience to produce optimal results and that are established or proposed as standard and suitable for widespread adoption. An important characteristic of the Best Practices shown in the Sustainable City App is that they are made by and focused on the community. As such, these best practices are divided into two categories: Best Practices to improve awareness at citizen level, and best practices to highlight green initiatives among local commerce. More information about the Best Practices view is available in Section 8.3.5

f) Learn More!

The purpose of the Learn More! view is to concentrate in a single space all the information that can help engage and educate citizens in the waste management system. As such, this view comprises features such a FAQ section, links to the materials and games developed within the

Waste4Think project, and also information about the ongoing PAYT regulation available in the municipality. More information about the Learn More! view is available on Section 8.3.6.

g) Profile Management

The Profile Management view allows the citizen to customize personal preferences of the app such as language, location permissions, type of notifications allowed or modified the credentials related to the accessibility of the Waste-O-Meter view. More information about the Profile Management view is available on Section 8.3.7.

8.2 Data model

The Waste4Think data model, defined in Section 7 of *Deliverable 2.1 Technical Documentation of R1: Operation and Management Module*, features a full-detailed definition of entities and attributes flexible enough to model and describe every stage of any waste management system:

- Definition of waste and cast categories used for waste characterization.
- Definition of sorting types in different countries.
- Definition of different waste deposit points: time scheduling, street/buried containers, door2door collection, deposit areas, clean points, industrial waste management using specialized deposit points, etc.
- Definition of vehicle types, vehicle and collection routes.
- Definition of waste transactions across different entities (users, deposit points, garbage trucks and treatment plants)
- Planification and results of Social Actions in each of the municipalities
- Operation of treatment plants
- KPIs for the evaluation of the performance of the waste management system among the different pilots

Specifically, the Sustainable City App (R6-R7) will make use of the following entities of the Waste4Think data model:

- a) **Dashboard:** SortingType, KeyPerformanceIndicator, Social Action, Best Practice
- b) **My Waste-O-Meter:** Waste, WasteCategory, SortingType, User, WasteTransaction, Invoice
- c) **Sort My Waste:** Waste, WasteCategory, SortingType, DepositPoint, DeposiPointType, DepositPointIsle
- d) **Bulletin Board:** Strategy, Social Action, Implementation
- e) **Best Practices:** Best Practices, Strategy, Action

8.3 Front-End design

With a fully responsive user interface (adaptative for different devices / screen sizes), the Sustainable City App is designed for optimal user experience. From a content design and user navigational point of view, the graphical elements relevant to how the information is going to be shown in the app are explained next.

a) Common layout

In order to give coherence and order the content on the Sustainable City, all views build their contents according to a common base layout. As seen in Figure 9, this layout features three well-defined areas:

- **Top left side area**, with the left-menu access and the logo of the Sustainable City App
- **Top right-side area**, with the main shortcuts and right-menu access
- **Main area**, where all the main content of the view will be displayed. It has been designed full width to include all the information needed for optimal user experience and will always display the icon of the current view.

Figure 9. Internal screen layout.

b) Left menu

 This is the main menu of the Sustainable City App. When the user clicks on this icon, the left-menu opens showing up the following options (see Figure 10. Left-side menu.):

- **Profile Management** redirects to the Profile Management view.
- **Dashboard** redirects to the Dashboard view.
- **Waste-O-Meter** redirects the Waste-O-Meter view.
- **Sort My Waste** redirect to the Sort My Waste view.
- **Bulletin Board:** redirects to the Bulletin Board view.
- **Best Practices** redirects to the Best Practices view.
- **Learn More!** redirects to the Learn More! view.
- **Tell us:** redirects to the Contact/Support view.
- **About:** redirects to the About view that contains information about the Privacy Policy.
- **Logout:** if logged in, allows the citizen to logout from the app.
- **Last sync at,** shows the date and time of the last update of the app.

Figure 10. Left-side menu.

c) Right menu

This is the secondary menu of the Sustainable City App. When the citizen clicks on it, the right-menu opens and shows the following options available from any view (Figure 11):

- **Filters**, shows the filtering options for the info/search result displayed.
- **Sort by**, allows to sort the information displayed alphabetically.
- **View options**, allows to show the information in a thumbnail view or by list.
- **Sync**, updates the last date/time info (last update)
- **Tell us**, redirects to the Contact/Support view of the app.

d) Main shortcuts

The following useful shortcuts are always visible at the right top navbar section of the screen and their functionalities are common across the app:

Dashboard, redirects to the Dashboard view (Section 8.3.1).

Notifications, redirects to the Notifications view (Section 8.3.7).

e) App logo

The Sustainable City App logo can be used as a shortcut to the Dashboard/Home when the citizen clicks on it. Currently, we are working on the real logo for the application, however for reference purposes we include the Waste4Think logo.

Figure 11. Right-side menu.

8.3.1 Dashboard

The **Dashboard** screen, also called “**Home**”, is the first view that appears when the citizen opens the Sustainable City App (Figure 12). The citizen can access it by using the 🏠 icon on the top navbar section, from the app logo, or from the Dashboard option on the left menu.

Figure 12. Dashboard screen.

As described in Section 8.1, the Dashboard provides pieces of information (widgets) where the citizen can get an overview of the whole information provided in the Sustainable City App. Every widget is clickable, and the citizen can check all details about it from its specific screen option. For example: if the citizen clicks on the widget “My waste sorting today”, the Waste-O-Meter section will be displayed.

8.3.2 My Waste-O-Meter

The Waste-O-Meter view is a private view that provides information about the interaction of the citizen with the waste management system in terms of access to the containers (openings of the electronic locks with the citizen card/citizen key), or number of used bags for residual waste. Since the information contained in this view is sensible and private, the citizen requires authentication to visualize the content.

- a) **Not logged in:** If the citizen is not logged in, the app will show the view on Figure 13 on access to the entry of the Waste-O-Meter on the left-side menu.

Figure 13. My Waste-O-Meter view (citizen not authenticated).

b) Logged in

If the citizen logs in (or is already logged in), the Waste-O-Meter view features two sections (Figure 14):

- A **graphical representation** of the waste generation performed by the citizen, with the specific inputs per sorting types and its monetary/points equivalence.
- **Filter options** that allow the citizen to choose the specific time range of consulting (yesterday, current day, week, month, last year, etc.)

Under this interactive area, the application can include some text to help the citizen translate the graphical information to a brief explanation.

Figure 14. My Waste-O-Meter view (citizen authenticated).

8.3.3 Sort My Waste

When the citizen clicks on the **Sort my Waste** entry of the left-menu, the view shows a list of available deposit points where the citizen can sort their waste. This list is shown according to the current location (geo-positioning coordinates) of the citizen, which is accessed by the application from GPS, Wi-Fi and mobile networks settings.

Sort my Waste includes:

- **Search tool.** A predictive and instant search tool where the citizen specifies the waste they need to sort. It will display the result (text and image) while the citizen is typing (Figure 15). For example, if the citizen types “pl”, the app will suggest items that may match those letters, such as “Apple”.
- **Sorting details.** The resulting outcome of the searched item: the characteristics of the waste (product, category), tips, and the location as well as information of the containers (deposit points) where the citizen can sort it (Figure 15). Note that an item may be sorted on more than one fraction. The available deposit points are shown with a colour tag glass according to their sorting type and include a brief information about their location, like postal code and region. The map locates the deposit points by using container icons 🗑️. The containers on the map can be clicked and the app will display their characteristics. Also, there are some options to display the information needed:
 - **View options**, to change how the info is displayed (list, thumbnails).
 - **Filter by**, to discriminate options according to the citizen needs (**¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.**).
 - **Order by**, to change the information order (ascending, descending).

Figure 15. Sort My Waste: instant/predictive search.

Figure 16. Sort My Waste: sorting details.

Figure 17. Sort My Waste: filter deposit points.

- Deposit point details.** When the citizen clicks on the icon, the view displays the specific information of the container (name, address, directions, website, contact number, customers reviews, etc.) (Figure 18; **Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.**).

Figure 18. Sort My Waste: deposit points details.

8.3.4 Bulletin Board

When the citizen clicks on the **Bulletin Board** entry on the left-menu, the view shows a list with information about notices, events, campaigns or ongoing collaborative actions that are taking place in the municipality both for residential and non-residential citizens (Figure 19). The citizen can filter the list based on given keywords or order the events alphabetically or chronologically.

Figure 19. Bulletin Board view.

8.3.5 Best Practices

When the citizen clicks on the **Best Practices** entry on the left-menu, the view shows information about best practices from the collaborative prevention actions and products and services from businesses with implemented best practices to optimize the environmental impact about the waste management and the citizen behaviour improvement. This view features three functionalities (Figure 20):

- **Best practices for citizens.** Features a list of ecological products and sustainable services that might be useful for improving the behaviour of the citizen through best practices on waste prevention. By default, all best practices are listed but this list can be customized according to filters defined by the citizen. (Figure 21).
- **Best practices for local trade.** List of local shops and business that follow green initiatives in local consumption and management of waste. By default, all best practices are listed but this list can be customized according to filters defined by the citizen. (Figure 22)
- **Share your best practice:** Features a form where the citizen can provide details of a new best practice to share with the rest of the community, whether focused on citizens

or on local trade (Figure 23). Citizen science activities focused on mapping either local commerce following green initiatives or individual recommendations for citizens can rely on this form to do so. More information about the use of this tool and the information gathered can be found in *Deliverable D4.2 Implementation of R17: ICT based Innovative Social Actions* and in Annex K of *Deliverable D1.3 Sustainability Assessment Models for information about the user requirements*.

Figure 20. Best practices view.

Figure 21. Best Practices: Best practices for citizens.

Figure 22. Best Practices: Best practices for local trade.

Figure 23. Best Practices: Share your best practice.

8.3.6 Learn More!

When the citizen clicks on the **Learn More!** entry on the left-menu, the view shows the following functionalities (Figure 24):

- **FAQ.** Short for frequently asked questions, this section features an online document that poses a series of common questions and answers regarding not only the waste management system, but also information about the use of the Sustainable City App.
- **Waste4Think materials.** Provides direct access to download the materials and games developed within the Waste4Think project: Ways2Sort, Eco Designer, Mayor's Table, and Virtual City (Deliverables 4.5-4.9)
- **PAYT regulation.** Provides links to the documents that detail the PAYT regulation active in the municipality.

• Figure 24. Learn More! view.

8.3.7 Profile management

When the citizen clicks on the dropdown arrow of left-menu, he/she can access to his/her account management options in the **Profile Management** view:

- **Language & location,** allows the citizen to set the preferred language and enable/disable his/her location information (Figure 25).

- **Notifications**, to see notifications and to enable/disable the notification preferences (Figure 27, Figure 27).

- *Figure 25. Profile management: language and Location*

Figure 26. Profile management: notification preferences.

Figure 27. Profile management: notifications.

- **Change password**, allows to change the password needed by the citizen to log in to access the Waste-O-Meter (Figure 28).

Figure 28. Profile management: change password.

8.4 Terms of Use

A special clause for the user to accept (explicitly) the Terms and Conditions of use for the app will be included, following the current regulations on this matter. It will be based on the example provided in Annex B, which is based on the conditions of the Waste App from the Urban Waste project GA No. 690452.

A special clause to inform the users no personal data will be handled will be included. In this App, FDeusto will not be the entity responsible for any process that involves personal data management.

These issues are under review of Waste4Think Ethical Committee.

References

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APPENDIXES OF D4.11 Technical Documentation of R5, R6 and R7: **Apps**

FDEUSTO

Type of document: Report

Dissemination level: Public

Reviewers: UPATRAS, ENBIO, SOFTLINE

Version	Date	Description of main changes	Author
1.0	06/02/2018	First draft	FDEUSTO
1.1	26/10/2018	Second draft (Citizen App & LocalTrade app merged)	FDEUSTO
2.0	29/11/2018	Edited according to reviewers' comments (major edition)	FDEUSTO
2.1	18/12/2018	Final version including reviewers' comments	FDEUSTO
2.2	24/05/2019	Responded to reviewer comments (major revision 2 ^o period)	FDEUSTO

Annex A: Draft of the Terms of Use of the Food App

1. This application is not suitable for people who are allergic or who have any food intolerance.
2. The DONOR COMPANY will not obtain neither economic retribution nor other type of retribution for the delivery to the receiving entity of the food through the FOODAPP. The RECEIVING COMPANY undertakes not to sell or use in any type of transaction the food received through the FOODAPP.
3. The DONOR COMPANY undertakes to always deliver the food in suitable conditions for consumption according to the opinion, where appropriate, of the authorized Health Technical Services. The RECEIVING COMPANY undertakes to keep the food in suitable conditions, paying special attention to the expiration dates and preferential consumption. Both entities are responsible for complying with the cold chain, as well as for complying with all the hygienic and sanitary conditions of food management, the DONOR COMPANY being RESPONSIBLE until the moment of donation. After the donation, the RECEIVING COMPANY undertakes to dispose of and use the administrative and operational capacity required to carry out the free distribution of the food delivered by the donor in optimum conditions and in order to comply with the required storage and cleaning requirements.
4. The truthfulness of the information contained in the FOODAPP concerning the food made available to the RECEIVING ENTITIES is the responsibility of the DONOR ENTITIES.

FDEUSTO, as the entity responsible for the FOODAPP, is not responsible for any damage caused by the poor state of the food derived from the non-observance of the previous commitments.

PRIVACY POLICY

The management of personal data of users will be carried out in the terms provided by the law, including the rights of opposition, access, rectification and cancelation of their personal data under the guidelines provided by the General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679. The FOODAPP user will be able to exercise these rights by writing a letter addressed to FDEUSTO - Deustotech, Energy & Environment unit, Avenida de las Universidades 24, 48007 Bilbao (Spain) or by email to secretaria.tech@deusto.es.

On acceptance of these Terms and Conditions, the user agrees to the collection, processing and communication of data of personal nature under the terms hereby established. The data requested by the FOODAPP is as follows:

- Contact data: on registration the user will be asked to provide the following data: name, CIF, number of employees, economic activity, telephone number and address (street, town, province, postal code, and country).
- Information about surplus: on creation of a new surplus, the user will be asked to provide information such as food name, photo, weight, pick up date, date of expiry, preferent consumption, food type, storage type, cold chain status, package type, surplus type, and cooked status.

- Data provided by the users of the FOODAPP will be handled by FDEUSTO and will be strictly used both for the provision of the service itself and for statistical purposes. The service features the following functionalities:
 - Visualization of the available surpluses in the area.
 - Identification of the characteristics of the surplus
 - Visualization of the statistics related to the donation activities of the user (kilocalories, water scarcity, etc.)
 - Visualization of best practices according to the economic activity of the user.
 - Bring together DONOR and DONEE to carry out the donation of surpluses. In order to make effective the transaction of the surplus between DONOR and DONEE, the only personal information of the DONORS that will be accessible to the DONEES is their name and location.

The data retention period will be the same as that of the users registered in the FOODAPP. When the FOODAPP is deleted, the data stored in the corresponding databases will be destroyed by FDEUSTO.

In the case a person declares he/she is under 18 years old and gets registered, his/her data will not be used and will be automatically deleted.

By accepting this, you agree with the terms and conditions included in these clauses.

Annex B: Draft of the Terms of Use of the Sustainable City App

1. Introduction

These Terms and Conditions shall manage your use of [APP_NAME] Application. These terms will be applied fully and affect to your use of [APP_NAME]. By using this application, you agree to accept all terms and conditions written in here. You must not use this application if you disagree with any of these Terms and Conditions. [APP_NAME] has been developed for the Waste4Think Research Project, under the funding of the EU H2020 program. The Waste4Think Consortium is formed by the partners of this project and the name of the cities, entities, companies and universities and their role can be found at <http://waste4think.eu/>. Minors or people below 18 years old are not allowed to use this application.

2. Intellectual Property rights

Other than the content you own, under these Terms Waste4Think Consortium and/or its licensors own all the intellectual property rights and material contained in this Application. You are granted limited license only for purposes of viewing and using the material contained on this Application.

3. Restrictions

Users are specifically restricted from all the following, at least without a specific permission from the Consortium:

- Publishing any material from this Application in any other media
- Selling, sublicensing and/or otherwise commercializing any application material; publicly performing and/or showing any material from this Application
- Using this application in any way that is or may be damaging the Application itself, or using this Application in any way that impacts user access to this Application
- Using this application contrary to applicable laws and regulations, or in any way may cause harm to the Application, or to any person or business entity
- Engaging in any data mining, data harvesting, data extracting or any other similar activity in relation to this Application; different that specifically admitted by the Waste4Think Consortium
- Using this Application to engage in any advertising or marketing, different than the specifically declared on this EU Research Project

Certain areas of this Application are restricted from being access by users and [Waste4Think Consortium may further restrict access by users to any areas of this Application, at any time, in absolute discretion. Neither confidential data nor data able to grant access to user's identity are acquired, stored or processed. By accepting these Terms and Conditions, user agrees with granting a permission for the installation and use of this Application in a specific device and agrees to allow the Waste4Think Consortium to acquire data regarding location information services on that device.

4. External contents

In these Terms and Conditions, "External Content" shall mean any audio, video, text, images or other material the User choose to display on this Application. [APP_NAME] is neither storing nor supporting displaying these Contents and [Waste4Think Consortium declines all responsibility on this. Waste4Think Consortium reserves the right to remove any Content from any user or participant on this Application at any time without notice. Specifically, no Waste4Think Consortium member, nor any of its officers, directors and employees, can be held liable by this External Contents in terms of legal property or invasion of any third-party's rights.

5. No warranties

This Application is provided “as is”, with all faults and Waste4Think Consortium express no representations or warranties, of any kind related to this Application or the materials contained on this Application. Also, nothing contained on this Application shall be interpreted as an advice for the users.

6. Limitation of Liability

In no event shall Waste4Think Consortium members, nor any of its officers, directors and employees, shall be held liable for anything arising out of or in any way connected with your use of this Application whether such liability is under contract. Waste4Think Consortium members, including its officers, directors and employees shall not be held liable for any indirect, consequential or special liability arising out of or in any way related the use of this Application.

7. Indemnification

The user hereby fully indemnifies Waste4Think Consortium from and against any and/or all liabilities, costs, demands, causes of action, damages and expenses arising in any way related to his/her breach of any of the provisions of these Terms.

8. Severability

If any provision of these Terms is found to be invalid under any applicable law, such provisions shall be deleted without affecting the remaining provisions herein.

9. Variation of Terms

The Waste4Think Consortium is permitted to revise these Terms at any time as it sees if, and by using this Application you are expected to review these Terms on a regular basis.

10. Assignment

The Waste4Think Consortium is allowed to assign, transfer, and subcontract its rights and/or obligations under these Terms without any notification. Any modification on the role or status of the participants on the Consortium can be also performed without any notification to the Users. However, users are not allowed to assign transfer or subcontract any of your right and/or obligations under these Terms.

11. Entire Agreement

These terms constitute the entire agreement between Urban waste consortium and the users in relation to their use of this application and supersede all prior agreements and understanding

12. Governing law & jurisdiction

These terms will be governed by and interpreted in accordance with the law of the Kingdom of Spain, and you submit to the non-exclusive jurisdiction of courts located in Spain for the resolution of any disputes. Specific injuries to contents provided by Waste4Think Consortium members can be also prosecuted under the National Laws of any country where the Application is used.

Comments from external reviewers

External reviewer 1

DATE: 29.05.2019

Issue	Yes	No	Score (1=low to 5=high)	Comments
Is the format of the document correct?	X		5	
Does the format of the document meet the objectives of the work done?	X		5	
Does the index of the document collect precisely the tasks and issues that need to be reported?	X		5	
Is the content of the document clear and well described?	X		5	
Does the content of each section describe the advance done during the task development?	X		5	
Does the content have sufficient technical description to make clear the research and development performed?	X		5	
Are all the figures and tables numerated and described?	X		5	
Are the indexes correct?	X		5	
Is the written English correct?	X		4	
Main technical terms are correctly referenced?	X		5	
Glossary present in the document?		X	3	

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External reviewer 2

DATE: 29.05.2019

Issue	Yes	No	Score (1=low to 5=high)	Comments
Is the format of the document correct?	X		5	
Does the format of the document meet the objectives of the work done?	X		5	
Does the index of the document collect precisely the tasks and issues that need to be reported?	X		5	
Is the content of the document clear and well described?	X		5	
Does the content of each section describe the advance done during the task development?	X		5	
Does the content have sufficient technical description to make clear the research and development performed?	X		5	
Are all the figures and tables numerated and described?	X		5	
Are the indexes correct?	X		5	
Is the written English correct?	X		4	
Main technical terms are correctly referenced?	X		5	
Glossary present in the document?		X	3	

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External Reviewer 3

DATE 29.05.2019

Issue	Yes	No	Score (1=low to 5=high)	Comments
Is the format of the document correct?	X		5	
Does the format of the document meet the objectives of the work done?	X		5	
Does the index of the document collect precisely the tasks and issues that need to be reported?	X		5	
Is the content of the document clear and well described?	X		5	
Does the content of each section describe the advance done during the task development?	X		4	Although there is no evidence of timeline of the development of the apps in the deliverable, it is clear that their design has taken a long process.
Does the content have sufficient technical description to make clear the research and development performed?	X		5	
Are all the figures and tables numerated and described?	X		5	
Are the indexes correct?	X		5	
Is the written English correct?	X		5	
Main technical terms are correctly referenced?	X		5	
Glossary present in the document?		X		All terms are well described, no glossary needed

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